

CREDIT SUPPORT FOR BUSINESS ENTITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Credit support for business entities in Uzbekistan plays an important role in diversifying the country's economy, creating new jobs and developing business. This article provides information on the current state of lending to small and medium-sized businesses in Uzbekistan, existing problems and ways to solve them. For the effective functioning of the business lending system, it is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the state and banks, simplify the loan application process and improve the provision of affordable loans. The article also discusses the impact of high interest rates on entrepreneurs and innovative areas of lending. The importance of financial support for entrepreneurship and its role in economic growth are highlighted.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, lending, small and medium-sized businesses, financial support, banks, interest rates, innovative loans, state programs, economic development, business development.

In Uzbekistan, credit support for business entities is one of the important elements of economic development. The development of entrepreneurship and support for small and medium-sized businesses is an integral part of the state's economic policy, which serves to diversify the country's economy, create new jobs and ensure social stability. Lending is of great importance in the financial support of business entities, since loans are a necessary tool for business expansion, the introduction of new technologies and increasing market share. The system of lending to business entities is developing in Uzbekistan. For several years, special

attention has been paid to financial support for small and medium-sized businesses in the country. Also, the provision of loans for the development of entrepreneurship through banks and other financial institutions is constantly expanding. A system of providing low-cost and long-term loans for small and medium-sized businesses has been introduced in the country. This, in turn, creates opportunities for entrepreneurs to implement innovative ideas, modernize production processes, launch new products, and increase their competitiveness.

In Uzbekistan, loans to business entities are mainly provided by banks and other financial institutions. Banks offer short-term and long-term loans to entrepreneurs, as well as subsidized loans allocated to entities by the state. In the process of obtaining a loan, entrepreneurs provide banks with various documents, business plans, and other necessary information. However, banks may set high interest rates on loans and require numerous guarantees from loan applicants. Thus, it may be difficult for entrepreneurs to obtain a loan in some cases. There are several problems with lending to business entities. First, many small and medium-sized businesses may not meet the strict lending conditions applied by banks. Banks usually require a large number of documents, business plans, the financial condition of the borrower, and many other guarantees to secure a loan. Such conditions are not easy for small businesses, since they often cannot provide guarantees or collateral. This, in turn, limits entrepreneurs' access to the financial resources they need to develop their businesses. The second problem is high interest rates.

Banks in Uzbekistan often set high interest rates for entrepreneurship, which can become a limiting factor for business development. This is especially important for start-up entrepreneurs and small businesses, as they cannot afford to take out high-interest loans. Banks are usually reluctant to lend to risky businesses, which leads to the provision of high interest rates. In addition, a lack of financial knowledge can also be a major problem for small businesses. Many entrepreneurs

lack financial literacy in managing and developing their businesses, so they have difficulty understanding and resolving the complexities that arise in the process of obtaining a loan. This, in turn, makes it difficult to access the loans needed to develop a business. Further improvement of the lending system is necessary for the development of small and medium-sized businesses in Uzbekistan. To do this, it is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the state and banks, provide affordable and long-term loans for businesses, as well as simplify the process of obtaining loans. For example, through special subsidized loan programs for small and medium-sized businesses, interest rates can be reduced and access to loans expanded. This will allow entrepreneurs to expand their businesses and introduce new technologies.

Also, when lending to entrepreneurs, special attention should be paid to supporting innovations and innovations. Financial support is necessary for the development of innovative businesses, since such businesses often involve high risks. Support from banks and other financial institutions is necessary for the introduction of innovative ideas and technologies, as well as for the conquest of new markets. The government of Uzbekistan is implementing a number of socio-economic programs for the development of entrepreneurship. In particular, there are programs aimed at making loans affordable for small and medium-sized businesses, as well as supporting innovative and technological development. Financial and legal support from the state, as well as the positive climate created for business development, contribute to the development of the economy, the creation of new jobs, ensuring economic growth and stability.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has also introduced many grants, subsidies, tax incentives and financial support instruments for small and medium-sized businesses. This will ensure stability in the economic situation and create new opportunities for entrepreneurs. The development of credit support for business entities in Uzbekistan is of great importance for the country's economy. It is

necessary to improve the lending system, provide affordable and long-term loans for small and medium-sized businesses, as well as strengthen cooperation between banks and entrepreneurs. Programs and support mechanisms developed by the Government of Uzbekistan allow for the development of small and medium-sized businesses. However, it is possible to support business entities more effectively by simplifying the processes of obtaining loans and reducing high interest rates, as well as increasing financial literacy.

Financial intermediation, as mentioned above, is the process of channeling funds between those who want to lend or invest and those who want to borrow or invest. Financial intermediaries play a key role by creating new financial assets and liabilities. A wide range of financial institutions are engaged in financial intermediation, including banks, insurance and pension companies, securities houses, etc. Most of the services provided by financial institutions include both intermediary and non-intermediary activities (e.g. payment services, fund management services, etc.). An important distinguishing feature of financial intermediation is that new financial assets and liabilities are created.

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